

**DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS OF YOUNG LEARNERS USING
INTERACTIVE QUIZZES IN ONLINE CLASSES**

D. Saidakhmedova¹

Abstract:

This article delves into the effectiveness of interactive quizzes in enhancing the speaking skills of young learners during online classes. Educators often grapple with maintaining student engagement and fostering communication abilities in virtual environments. The study investigates various quiz formats, including multiple-choice, fill-in-the-blank, and short-answer questions. It emphasizes the importance of considering students' emotional and psychological challenges. To address these hurdles, the article proposes an interactive activity-based model for speaking practice.

Key words: speaking skills, young learners, interactive methods, online classes, communication abilities, student motivation, educational environment.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/vvz7p239>

As we know speaking is the communication way between individuals which represents ideas to others. The vast majority of human beings communicate orally and naturally in a reliable way. Whether it is formal or informal speaking always be the main part of life. In addition to this developing strong speaking competence requires permanent practice. "Showing the talent instead of creating it is much more difficult and takes more effort than other things. The actress or an actor will not get the award by reading the written script, even if they learn by heart these lines. The way the actress plays and impresses the audience matters more than heart-touching lines. If people want to be competent speakers need to think about typical speaking standards" (Palmer, 2014, p.2). As speaking is one of the parts of integrated skills, teaching speaking allows language learners to convey their words clearly and correctly. This skill shows an intellectual capacity to reflect a learner's thoughts, feelings, and mind. So, students will be able to perform communicatively. Consequently, teaching integrated skills has changed over the years respectively. Since COVID-19 has spread all over the world educational institutions noticeably have changed the way of teaching the subjects. To prevent this virus all systems switched to online mode. Like other systems, educational establishments also shifted to online and this way has brought both comforts and challenges among educators and learners. Online teaching created a much better atmosphere than offline classes for individuals such as attending lessons while staying at home and saving precious time.

However, as the coins have two sides online learning especially in speaking skills has drawbacks as well. Conducting the lessons, especially teaching foreign languages to young learners can be challenging. Every child has a short span of

¹ Saidakhmedova. D.S., MA TESOL graduate student at Webster University in Tashkent

attention which means they cannot concentrate on one thing for more than 14 to 15 minutes and this means that an efficient work coefficient will be lower rather than expected. Secondly, linguistic difficulties when learners do not know the average vocabulary range to speak mostly occur when they have limited focus or get bored with the lesson. Another point is that inhibition. Inhibition is a fear of speaking which stops you from expressing your real thoughts or ideas. And it happens when people need to speak with others. As Kumaradivelu (2003) outlined language is best learned when learners' attention focuses on understanding, using, and doing something with the language, but not on explicitly analyzing its features. (p.27) The last one is providing repetitions and drills as a domain practice in the lessons. These are the focal parts of problems in EFL classes in which language learners struggle. These are the obstacles that most EFL teachers struggle to implement in their speaking lessons.

Games with quizzes help with information retention, focus, confidence building, and identifying knowledge gaps. Also, they help to hold learner's attention and keep them active. Al-Sibai et al. (2004, p. 3 as cited in Al-Hosni et al., 2014) showed that one of the most popular yet intricate activities in English language instruction is oral communication in English as a foreign language (EFL) or as a second language (ESL). This is particularly valid now, as being able to communicate effectively in English is becoming more and more important for growth in a variety of human endeavors. "While input is widely recognised as essential for language acquisition, it alone is insufficient. Interaction and output (the language the learner produces) are crucial complements. This is because comprehension and production involve distinct cognitive processes. Understanding the meaning conveyed in sentences differs from effectively utilising a linguistic system to express oneself. To improve the lack of attention in younger learners, mentors should consider working effectively within these 14-15 minutes. Using interactive quizzes, and handouts can easily attract children to lessons. To help them focus and refuel, learners should be encouraged to take brief breaks every 15 to 20 minutes. Incorporate practical exercises and assignments that enable kids to apply what they've learned. When the input is negotiated and learners engage in interactive output, they actively focus on comprehensible portions of the input and select appropriate linguistic forms for self-expression. This process facilitates the internalization of learned concepts and experiences," as highlighted by Swain (1985, as cited in Zhang, 2009). Addressing the gamification in lessons, the issues of domain repetition and drills in online learning might decrease. Adding some features of a game, such as points, badges, leaderboards, quizzes, flashcards, and awards, to drills and repetition to make them more interesting and fun for younger students. Moreover, making use of interactive resources like discussion boards, polls, and quizzes to motivate young students to participate in the content and contribute their opinions also helps to increase speaking skills as well. It is true that incorporating interactive games, quizzes, and tools such as those listed above can aid in preventing attention and engagement problems in online learning settings. Teachers may give their pupils a more engaging and dynamic learning environment by making learning enjoyable and participatory. Additionally, gamification components and technology utilisation can improve student engagement, motivation, and language proficiency. By utilising these tools, educators can design captivating classes that accommodate the many learning preferences and styles of young students, leading to a more successful and pleasurable educational process.

There are various interactive quizzes, sites can help to engage students in speaking. Here are some of the good options to catch students' attention in the classes:

www.thelearningapps.com – it strives to provide the best educational apps, empowering teachers and parents to facilitate learning through technology. The engaging apps combine fun and learning for children, covering topics from basic animal names and sounds and alphabets and numbers to even complex math and physics concepts. All apps are interactive and user-friendly, ensuring a smooth learning experience. This site is built for younger learners who are learning very basic knowledge of English and it represents geographical quizzes to interact with kids with a variety of images and games, stories and printables.

www.english-4kids.com – basically, this website is for parents and teachers who are trying to help children learn the English language. It is one of the newest teaching sites which is full of e-sources for conducting online classes. It provides different materials such as, fun games, worksheets, tutorials and ready-made PPTs (PowerPoint slides) for teachers.

www.englishclub.com - this is the top-ranked site which can easily engage students in online classes. With the help of e-resources, both students and teachers can work cooperatively. This club helps to learn English or teach English as a second language. Access to all pages is free. People can use the colour-coded star on the right or the tabs at the top to help navigate the site. Teachers and students find everything from lessons for learners to jobs for teachers, including many interactive pages such as forums, games, quizzes, chat, and ESL penpals. This platform has preferences to use in class and can guide you with effective exercises and tests.

www.play.blooket.com/play - it reimagines the modern classroom review game with an exciting twist, blending action and education to create the ultimate learning experience. With detailed score reports and question analysis, teachers gain valuable insights into student performance, pinpointing areas that require further review.

www.wordwall.com - this website is also becoming more common among language teachers and learners. It creates very interactive and engaging activities, and games which can improve students' knowledge of languages, with these sorts of features EFL teachers will conduct effective lessons to improve grammar and speaking.

www.twinkl.co.uk - this site represents various digital teaching materials which teachers use to improve students' integrated skills. Mostly this site is created for international markets and language schools. A wide variety of teacher-generated resources, including lesson plans, teaching strategies, and classroom management, are available on Twinkl. This covers everything from motivating posters and classroom display ideas to materials for school celebrations, parental tips, at-home learning, and family activities.

www.nearpod.com – online educational teaching platform for school teachers to utilize quizzes, games, slides, activities and videos. A computerised tool called Nearpod helps teachers teach more effectively. With tools for instruction and student participation, it enables you to build and present interactive slide-based classes. For even more versatility, Nearpod easily connects with other well-known programs like YouTube, Google Slides, and Microsoft PowerPoint.

References:

- [1]. Al-Hosni, S. (2014). *Speaking difficulties encountered by young EFL learners. International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature (IJSELL) Vol. 2, Issue 6, June 2014, PP 22-30*
- [2]. Kumaravadivelu, B. (2003). *Beyond methods. London: Yale University Press.*
- [3]. Palmer, E. (2014). *Teaching the core skills of listening and speaking. ASCD.*
- [4]. Zhang, S. (2009). *The role of input, interaction, and output in the development of oral fluency. English Language Teaching, 2(4), 91–100.*